

A guide to selecting high-performing antibodies for CTHRC1 (Q96CG8) for use in western blot and immunoprecipitation

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Abstract

Collagen triple helix repeat-containing protein 1 (CTHRC1) is a secreted glycoprotein that plays a key role in tissue remodeling, cell migration, and extracellular matrix regulation. Here we have characterized nine CTHRC1 commercial antibodies for western blot and immunoprecipitation using a standardized experimental protocol based on comparing read-outs in knockout cell lines and isogenic parental controls. These studies are part of a larger, collaborative initiative seeking to address antibody reproducibility issues by characterizing commercially available antibodies for human proteins and publishing the results openly as a resource for the scientific community. While the use of antibodies and protocols vary between laboratories, we encourage readers to use this report as a guide to select the most appropriate antibodies for their specific needs.

Keywords:

UniProt ID: Q96CG8, *CTHRC1*, CTHRC1, Collagen triple helix repeat-containing protein 1, antibody characterization, antibody validation, western blot, immunoprecipitation

Introduction

CTHRC1 is a secreted extracellular matrix-associated protein that has emerged as a critical regulator of tissue remodeling and cellular motility [1]. CTHRC1 modulates key signaling pathways, including Wnt/planar cell polarity (PCP) and transforming growth factor- β (TGF- β), thereby influencing neuronal migration, axonal guidance, and cytoskeletal organization [2].

This research is part of a broader collaborative initiative in which academics, funders and commercial antibody manufacturers are working together to address antibody reproducibility issues by characterizing commercial antibodies for human proteins using standardized protocols, and openly sharing the data [3]. It consists of identifying human cell lines with adequate target protein expression and the development/contribution of equivalent knockout (KO) cell lines, followed by antibody characterization procedures using most commercially available renewable antibodies against the corresponding protein [3]. Here we characterized nine commercial CTHRC1 antibodies, selected and donated by participant antibody manufacturers, for use in western blot and immunoprecipitation enabling biochemical and cellular assessment of CTHRC1 properties and function. As CTHRC1 is a secreted protein, antibodies were not evaluated in immunofluorescence.

The authors do not engage in result analysis or offer explicit antibody recommendations. Our primary aim is to deliver top-tier data to the scientific community, grounded in Open Science principles. This empowers experts to interpret the characterization data independently, enabling them to make informed choices regarding the most suitable antibodies for their specific experimental needs. Guidelines on how to interpret antibody characterization data found in this study are featured on the YCharOS gateway [4] and in Table 4 of this data note [3].

Results and discussion

Our standard protocol involves comparing readouts from wild type (WT) and KO cell lines [5]. In the absence of commercially available KO cell lines, siRNA technology can be employed to knockdown (KD) the target gene [6, 7]. To determine which cell line demonstrates high expression of CTHRC1, we examined the DepMap (Cancer Dependency Map Portal, RRID:SCR_017655) transcriptomics database to identify cell lines that express the target at levels greater than $2.5 \log_2$ (transcripts per million “TPM” + 1), which we have found to be a suitable cut-off [8]. The cell line A-375 expresses the *CTHRC1* transcript at $6.1 \log_2$ TPM+ 1 and was thus selected as appropriate for KD. A non-targeting control siRNA pool was used to treat A-375 control (ctrl) cells, while *CTHRC1* was KD using a pool of siRNA targeting this gene.

To screen all nine by western blot, ctrl and *CTHRC1* KD protein lysates were ran on SDS-PAGE, transferred onto nitrocellulose membranes, and then probed with the nine CTHRC1 antibodies in parallel (Figure 1).

We then assessed the capability of all nine antibodies to capture CTHRC1 from A-375 WT protein extracts using immunoprecipitation techniques, followed by western blot analysis. For the immunoblot step, a

specific CTHRC1 antibody identified previously (refer to Figure 1) was selected. Equal amounts of the starting material (SM) and the unbound fractions (UB), as well as the whole immunoprecipitate (IP) eluates were separated by SDS-PAGE (Figure 2).

In conclusion, we have screened nine CTHRC1 commercial antibodies by western blot, and immunoprecipitation by comparing the signal produced by the antibodies in human A-375 ctrl and *CTHRC1* KD cells. To assist users in interpreting antibody performance, Table 4 outlines various scenarios in which antibodies may perform in all three applications [8]. High-quality and renewable antibodies that successfully detect CTHRC1 were identified in both applications. Researchers who wish to study CTHRC1 in a different species are encouraged to select high-quality antibodies, based on the results of this study, and investigate the predicted species reactivity of the manufacturer before extending their research.

Limitations

Inherent limitations are associated with the antibody characterization platform used in this study. Firstly, the YCharOS project focuses on renewable (recombinant and monoclonal) antibodies and does not test all commercially available CTHRC1 antibodies. YCharOS partners provide approximately 80% of all renewable antibodies, but some top-cited polyclonal antibodies may not be available through these partners. We encourage readers to consult vendor documentation to identify the specific antigen each antibody is raised against, where such information is available.

Secondly, the YCharOS effort employs a non-biased approach that is agnostic to the protein for which antibodies have been characterized. The aim is to provide objective data on antibody performance without preconceived notions about how antibodies should perform or the molecular weight that should be observed in western blot. As the authors are not experts in CTHRC1, only a brief overview of the protein's function and its relevance in disease is provided. CTHRC1 experts are invited to analyze and interpret observed banding patterns in western blots.

Thirdly, YCharOS experiments are not performed in replicates primarily due to the use of multiple antibodies targeting various epitopes. Once a specific antibody is identified, it validates the protein expression of the intended target in the selected cell line, confirms the lack of protein expression in the KO cell line and supports conclusions regarding the specificity of the other antibodies. All experiments are performed using master mixes, and meticulous attention is paid to sample preparation and experimental execution. In IF, the use of two different concentrations serves to evaluate antibody specificity and can aid in assessing assay reliability. In instances where antibodies yield no signal, a repeat experiment is conducted following titration. Additionally, our independent data is performed subsequently to the antibody manufacturers internal validation process, therefore making our characterization process a repeat.

Lastly, as comprehensive and standardized procedures are respected, any conclusions remain confined to the experimental conditions and cell line used for this study. The use of a single cell type for evaluating antibody performance poses as a limitation, as factors such as target protein abundance significantly impact results. Additionally, the use of cancer cell lines containing gene mutations poses a potential challenge, as these mutations may be within the epitope coding sequence or other regions of the gene responsible for the intended target. Such alterations can impact the binding affinity of antibodies. This represents an inherent limitation of any approach that employs cancer cell lines.

Method

The standardized protocols used to carry out this KO-based antibody characterization platform was established and approved by a collaborative group of academics, industry researchers and antibody manufacturers. The detailed materials and step-by-step protocols used to characterize antibodies in western blot, immunoprecipitation and immunofluorescence are openly available on Protocols.io ([protocols.io/view/a-consensus-platform-for-antibody-characterization](https://www.protocols.io/view/a-consensus-platform-for-antibody-characterization)) [3]. Brief descriptions of the experimental setup used to carry out this study can be found below.

Cell lines and antibodies

The cell lines, primary and secondary antibodies used in this study are listed in Table 1, 2, and 3, respectively. To ensure consistency with manufacturer recommendations and account for proprietary formulations (where antibody concentrations are not disclosed), antibody usage is reported as dilution ratios rather than absolute concentrations. To facilitate proper citation and unambiguous identification, all cell lines and antibodies are referenced with their corresponding Research Resource Identifiers (RRIDs) [9, 10]. All cell lines used in this study were regularly tested for mycoplasma contamination and were confirmed to be mycoplasma-free.

To knockdown *CTHRC1*, A-375 cells were treated with the *CTHRC1* SMARTPool from Horizon Discovery (cat. number L-015487-01) for five days. A-375 control cells were treated with the ON-TARGETplus Non-targeting Control Pool (Horizon Discovery, cat. number D-001810-10). Lipofectamine RNAiMAX (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 13778030) was used to transfect the siRNA following the manufacturer's protocol.

Antibody screening by western blot

A-375 ctrl and *CTHRC1* KD cells were collected in RIPA buffer (25mM Tris-HCl pH 7.6, 150mM NaCl, 1% NP-40, 1% sodium deoxycholate, 0.1% SDS) (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 89901) supplemented with 1x protease inhibitor cocktail mix (MilliporeSigma, cat. number P8340). Lysates were sonicated briefly and incubated 30 min on ice. Lysates were spun at $\sim 110,000 \times g$ for 15 min at 4°C and equal protein aliquots of the supernatants were analyzed by SDS-PAGE and western blot. BLUelf prestained protein ladder (GeneDireX, cat. number PM008-0500) was used.

Western blots were performed with precast midi 10% Bis-Tris polyacrylamide gels (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number WG1201BOX) ran with MES SDS buffer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number NP000202), loaded in LDS sample buffer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number NP0008) with 1x sample reducing agent (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number NP0009) and transferred on nitrocellulose membranes. Proteins on the blots were visualized with Ponceau S staining (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number BP103-10) which is scanned to show together with individual western blot. Blots were blocked with 5% milk for 1 hr, and antibodies were incubated O/N at 4°C with 5% milk in TBS with 0,1% Tween 20 (TBST) (Cell Signalling Technology, cat. number 9997). Following three washes with TBST, the peroxidase

conjugated secondary antibody was incubated with the membrane in TBST with 5% milk for 1 hr at room temperature followed by three washes with TBST. Membranes were incubated with Pierce ECL (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 32106) prior to detection with the iBright™ CL1500 Imaging System (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number A44240).

Antibody screening by immunoprecipitation

Antibody-bead conjugates were prepared by adding 2µg to 500 µl of Pierce IP Lysis Buffer from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 87788) in a microcentrifuge tube, together with 30 µl of Dynabeads protein A- (for rabbit antibodies) or protein G- (for mouse antibodies) (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 10002D and 10004D, respectively). All tubes were rocked for ~1 h at 4°C followed by two washes to remove unbound antibodies.

A-375 WT were collected in Pierce IP buffer (25 mM Tris-HCl pH 7.4, 150 mM NaCl, 1 mM EDTA, 1% NP-40 and 5% glycerol) supplemented with protease inhibitor. Lysates were rocked 30 min at 4°C and spun at 110,000 x g for 15 min at 4°C. 0.5 ml aliquots at 1 mg/ml of lysate were incubated with an antibody-bead conjugate for ~1 h at 4°C. The unbound fractions were collected, and beads were subsequently washed three times with 1.0 ml of IP buffer and processed for SDS-PAGE and western blot on precast midi 10% Bis-Tris polyacrylamide gels.

Data availability

Underlying data

Zenodo: Dataset for the CTHRC1 antibody screening study <to be submitted>

Data are available under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license (CC-BY 4.0).

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Competing interests

For this project, the authors developed partnerships with leading antibody manufacturers and KD cell line providers. The partners provide antibodies and KD cell lines to this project at no cost. These partners include: Abcam, ABCD antibodies, ABclonal, Addgene, Aviva Systems Biology, BioTechne, Cell Signaling Technology, Developmental Studies Hybridoma Bank, GeneTex, Horizon Discovery, Institute for Protein Innovation, MilliporeSigma, Proteintech, Synaptic Systems, Thermo Fisher Scientific.

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Table 1: Summary of the cell lines used

Institution	Catalog number	RRID (Cellosaurus)	Cell line	Genotype
ATCC	CRL-1619	CVCL_0132	A-375	WT

Table 2: Summary of the CTHRC1 antibodies tested

Company	Catalog number	Lot number	RRID (Antibody Registry)	Clonality	Clone ID	Host	Concentration ($\mu\text{g}/\mu\text{L}$)	Vendors recommended applications
Abbexa	abx422626**	A2511596E	AB_3739798	recombinant mono	B593	rabbit	1.00	Wb
Abcam	ab256458**	1113983-2	AB_3096210	recombinant mono	EPR22851-145	rabbit	0.60	Wb, IP
Abcam	ab274446**	1011557-1	AB_3741465	recombinant mono	EPR22851-144	rabbit	1.05	other
Abcam	ab274447**	1100222-4	AB_3741466	recombinant mono	EPR22851-215	rabbit	0.94	other
Aviva Systems Biology	ARP59864_P050	QC30786-200327	AB_3698286	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.50	Wb
Proteintech	16534-1-AP	00159595	AB_2087511	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.55	Wb, IP, IF
Proteintech	83629-1-RR**	23008675	AB_3671242	recombinant mono	240442E1	rabbit	1.00	Wb
Thermo Fisher Scientific	MA5-29201**	79532302	AB_2785113	recombinant mono	166	rabbit	1.00	Wb, IP
Thermo Fisher Scientific	MA5-34885*	79532282	AB_2848792	monoclonal	5H1	mouse	2.00	Wb

Wb=western blot; IP=immunoprecipitation; IF= immunofluorescence, **= recombinant antibody, *= monoclonal antibody, NA=not available

Table 3: Table of secondary antibodies used

Company	Secondary antibody	Catalog number	RRID (Antibody Registry)	Clonality	Concentration (µg/µL)	Working concentration (µg/mL)
Proteintech	HRP-Goat Anti-Rabbit Antibody (H+L)	RGAR001	AB_3073505	recombinant polyclonal	1.0	0.05
Proteintech	HRP-Goat Anti-Mouse Antibody (H+L)	RGAM001	AB_3068333	recombinant polyclonal	1.0	0.5
Cell Signaling Technology	Protein A, HRP conjugate	12291	NA	polyclonal	0.125	0.5

Table 4: Illustrations to assess antibody performance in all western blot, immunoprecipitation and immunofluorescence

This table has been reproduced with permission from Ayoubi et al., Elife, 2023 [8]

Figure 1: CTHRC1 antibody screening by western blot

Figure 2: CTHRC1 antibody screening by immunoprecipitation

FIGURE LEGENDS

Figure 1: CTHRC1 antibody screening by western blot.

Lysates of A-375 ctrl and *CTHRC1* KD were prepared, and 30 µg of protein were processed for western blot with the indicated CTHRC1 antibodies. The Ponceau stained transfers of each blot are presented to show equal loading of ctrl and KD lysates and protein transfer efficiency from the acrylamide gels to the nitrocellulose membrane. Antibody dilutions were chosen according to the recommendations of the antibody supplier. Antibody dilutions used: abx422626** at 1/1000, ab256458** at 1/1000, ab274446** at 1/500, ab274447** at 1/500, ARP59864_P050 at 1/500, 16534-1-AP at 1/2000, 83629-1-RR** at 1/5000, MA5-29201** at 1/500, MA5-34885* at 1/500. Predicted band size: 26 kDa. **= recombinant antibody, *= monoclonal antibody.

Figure 2: CTHRC1 antibody screening by immunoprecipitation.

A-375 lysates were prepared, and immunoprecipitation was performed for 1 h using 0.5 mg of lysate and 2.0 µg of the indicated CTHRC1 antibodies pre-coupled to Dynabeads protein A or protein G. Samples were washed and processed for western blot with anti-CTHRC1 83629-1-RR** used at 1/3000. The Ponceau stained transfers of each blot are shown. SM=6% starting material; UB=6% unbound fraction; IP=immunoprecipitate. **= recombinant antibody, *= monoclonal antibody.